

Supplementary table S3. Information of the differentially expressed genes at W of the wild type (WT) and the mutant (MU).

	GeneID	$\log_2^{(FPKM_WT/FPKM_MU)}$	P-value
Up regulated in MU			
	BMSK0004212.1	-9.7621	0.0000
	BMSK0004222.1	-14.2895	0.0000
	BMSK0009013.1	-8.2529	0.0000
	BMSK0010015.1	-6.3234	0.0000
	BMSK0004217.1	-6.7600	0.0000
	BMSK0004449.1	-4.6419	0.0000
	BMSK0015969.1	-8.4407	0.0000
	BMSK0000963.1	-9.9262	0.0000
	BMSK0011519.1	-6.8609	0.0000
	BMSK0001308.1	-6.8258	0.0000
	BMSK0008956.1	-2.6227	0.0000
	BMSK0000965.1	-8.8663	0.0000
	BMSK0010020.1	-8.6560	0.0000
	BMSK0003085.1	-5.1449	0.0000
	BMSK0007028.1	-1.9845	0.0000
	BMSK0006632.1	-6.2591	0.0000
	BMSK0008976.1	-2.8902	0.0000
	BMSK0013818.1	-5.0965	0.0000
	BMSK0011069.1	-2.3266	0.0000
	BMSK0009711.1	-5.3231	0.0000
	BMSK0008962.1	-1.8119	0.0000
	BMSK0000966.1	-4.7014	0.0000
	BMSK0004969.1	-2.7322	0.0000
	BMSK0005309.1	-4.2582	0.0000
	BMSK0012279.1	-5.2135	0.0000
	BMSK0013661.1	-5.8605	0.0000
	BMSK0013494.1	-5.3539	0.0000
	BMSK0006071.1	-2.8251	0.0000
	BMSK0011523.1	-5.0659	0.0000
	BMSK0011522.1	-4.9098	0.0000
	BMSK0010300.1	-4.7113	0.0000
	BMSK0013673.1	-2.3020	0.0000
	BMSK0001189.1	-3.2692	0.0000
	BMSK0011524.1	-4.9799	0.0000
	BMSK0012866.1	-1.6455	0.0000
	BMSK0012818.1	-1.9470	0.0000
	BMSK0000961.1	-7.4240	0.0000
	BMSK0003626.1	-7.0180	0.0000
	BMSK0005375.1	-3.2869	0.0000
	BMSK0006280.1	-3.0135	0.0000
	BMSK0002252.1	-2.5393	0.0000
	BMSK0015240.1	-4.8950	0.0000
	BMSK0013821.1	-5.4379	0.0000
	BMSK0015392.1	-6.7507	0.0000
	BMSK0013429.1	-3.7921	0.0000
	BMSK0005619.1	-4.3413	0.0000
	BMSK0013820.1	-7.0659	0.0000
	BMSK0005041.1	-5.1373	0.0000
	BMSK0002258.1	-4.6919	0.0000
	BMSK0010730.1	-2.7832	0.0000
	BMSK0000964.1	-7.3248	0.0000
	BMSK0015767.1	-3.9511	0.0000
	BMSK0006863.1	-3.6274	0.0000
	BMSK0004704.1	-3.8273	0.0000
	BMSK0013391.1	-4.9319	0.0000
	BMSK0015395.1	-7.6435	0.0000
	BMSK0005712.1	-4.0601	0.0000
	BMSK0011511.1	-3.9665	0.0000
	BMSK0012979.1	-2.3158	0.0000
	BMSK0002515.1	-4.2186	0.0000

BMSK0012694.1	-2.2574	0.0000
BMSK0012978.1	-1.6916	0.0000
BMSK0015818.1	-2.6231	0.0000
BMSK0006869.1	-2.9392	0.0000
BMSK0008910.1	-3.7099	0.0000
BMSK0011521.1	-4.9903	0.0000
BMSK0011452.1	-7.4482	0.0000
BMSK0011517.1	-4.4949	0.0000
BMSK0010342.1	-2.8559	0.0000
BMSK0007404.1	-4.0486	0.0000
BMSK0003942.1	-1.8244	0.0000
BMSK0000978.1	-6.7723	0.0000
BMSK0000548.1	-1.4207	0.0000
BMSK0015397.1	-5.6469	0.0000
BMSK0010302.1	-4.6314	0.0000
BMSK0013260.1	-2.9557	0.0000
BMSK0003012.1	-4.1570	0.0000
BMSK0010014.1	-6.2801	0.0000
BMSK0011163.1	-4.4851	0.0000
BMSK0005719.1	-4.9373	0.0000
BMSK0000962.1	-6.4120	0.0000
BMSK0015032.1	-5.6618	0.0000
BMSK0008271.1	-4.5522	0.0000
BMSK0011552.1	-2.3775	0.0000
BMSK0014791.1	-7.9189	0.0000
BMSK0006495.1	-4.7036	0.0000
BMSK0013078.1	-1.8679	0.0000
BMSK0010360.1	-6.7492	0.0000
BMSK0007400.1	-6.1420	0.0000
BMSK0011795.1	-3.1539	0.0000
BMSK0010818.1	-4.3083	0.0000
BMSK0004871.1	-4.1996	0.0000
BMSK0006132.1	-2.2416	0.0000
BMSK0006870.1	-3.4203	0.0000
BMSK0013394.1	-3.3801	0.0000
BMSK0004901.1	-2.6351	0.0000
BMSK0007395.1	-1.9494	0.0000
BMSK0010779.1	-4.0270	0.0000
BMSK0007473.1	-6.1631	0.0000
BMSK0008903.1	-4.6899	0.0000
BMSK0004161.1	-2.3868	0.0000
BMSK0007272.1	-1.3335	0.0000
BMSK0012727.1	-2.0457	0.0000
BMSK0006360.1	-4.6534	0.0000
BMSK0004162.1	-2.2864	0.0000
BMSK0011693.1	-1.8382	0.0000
BMSK0004719.1	-3.3304	0.0000
BMSK0009146.1	-2.6584	0.0000
BMSK0007001.1	-2.6189	0.0000
BMSK0010863.1	-2.8398	0.0000
BMSK0005295.1	-1.6893	0.0000
BMSK0007255.1	-1.9041	0.0000
BMSK0015780.1	-3.5716	0.0000
BMSK0011518.1	-4.1758	0.0000
BMSK0005087.1	-2.0745	0.0000
BMSK0003409.1	-4.3429	0.0000
BMSK0008304.1	-2.1491	0.0000
BMSK0013357.1	-2.6294	0.0000
BMSK0011560.1	-1.4750	0.0000
BMSK0003031.1	-5.8658	0.0000
BMSK0011863.1	-3.0068	0.0000
BMSK0010696.1	-1.9947	0.0000
BMSK0003562.1	-4.2842	0.0000

BMSK0003013.1	-5.4017	0.0000
BMSK0016060.1	-3.5698	0.0000
BMSK0013968.1	-2.2347	0.0000
BMSK0001014.1	-1.4296	0.0000
BMSK0004169.1	-1.7773	0.0000
BMSK0012941.1	-6.3858	0.0000
BMSK0008566.1	-2.0601	0.0000
BMSK0012695.1	-1.9459	0.0000
BMSK0005701.1	-5.1769	0.0000
BMSK0010428.1	-2.1552	0.0001
BMSK0014705.1	-1.4886	0.0001
BMSK0001975.1	-3.6679	0.0001
BMSK0005620.1	-1.9607	0.0001
BMSK0004184.1	-2.1375	0.0001
BMSK0011839.1	-2.5926	0.0001
BMSK0015917.1	-2.6470	0.0001
BMSK0009145.1	-2.3234	0.0001
BMSK0004756.1	-2.4417	0.0001
BMSK0008122.1	-1.6142	0.0001
BMSK0003511.1	-3.4794	0.0001
BMSK0013679.1	-4.4058	0.0001
BMSK0004739.1	-2.8453	0.0001
BMSK0009010.1	-6.2434	0.0001
BMSK0006107.1	-2.1726	0.0001
BMSK0016062.1	-1.6175	0.0001
BMSK0006505.1	-3.3175	0.0001
BMSK0015375.1	-3.2402	0.0001
BMSK0009263.1	-3.5719	0.0001
BMSK0000177.1	-5.3174	0.0001
BMSK0015110.1	-1.7135	0.0001
BMSK0007289.1	-2.6927	0.0002
BMSK0001401.1	-1.9527	0.0002
BMSK0005892.1	-5.5297	0.0002
BMSK0001429.1	-1.4384	0.0002
BMSK0011305.1	-3.5856	0.0002
BMSK0004175.1	-6.0912	0.0002
BMSK0016001.1	-1.7662	0.0002
BMSK0010378.1	-3.2265	0.0002
BMSK0007204.1	-3.9775	0.0002
BMSK0012210.1	-5.4974	0.0002
BMSK0002560.1	-3.4234	0.0002
BMSK0009979.1	-1.6655	0.0002
BMSK0015393.1	-7.2454	0.0002
BMSK0006605.1	-2.6968	0.0002
BMSK0006315.1	-2.6999	0.0002
BMSK0012937.1	-1.7924	0.0002
BMSK0004232.1	-4.1029	0.0002
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BMSK0005893.1	-1.3124	0.0002
BMSK0006429.1	-3.7052	0.0002
BMSK0009900.1	-1.6994	0.0002
BMSK0010538.1	-1.9348	0.0002
BMSK0004088.1	-3.5581	0.0002
BMSK0006868.1	-2.4452	0.0002
BMSK0008953.1	-1.7427	0.0002
BMSK0006070.1	-3.6280	0.0002
BMSK0016069.1	-1.2011	0.0003
BMSK0015557.1	-1.6345	0.0003
BMSK0013599.1	-2.2954	0.0003
BMSK0013617.1	-2.3017	0.0003
BMSK0009006.1	-1.5123	0.0003
BMSK0011030.1	-6.4967	0.0003
BMSK0007253.1	-2.2299	0.0003

BMSK0006832.1	-2.2892	0.0003
BMSK0012537.1	-3.1728	0.0003
BMSK0014385.1	-1.1837	0.0003
BMSK0013144.1	-2.7821	0.0003
BMSK0010840.1	-1.7198	0.0003
BMSK0003730.1	-5.8589	0.0003
BMSK0012662.1	-1.3746	0.0003
BMSK0009693.1	-4.4273	0.0003
BMSK0005298.1	-2.4126	0.0003
BMSK0010123.1	-1.2273	0.0003
BMSK0003719.1	-5.4905	0.0004
BMSK0009279.1	-3.3210	0.0004
BMSK0005488.1	-1.5489	0.0004
BMSK0007401.1	-5.8441	0.0004
BMSK0013320.1	-1.4184	0.0004
BMSK0011526.1	-5.0111	0.0004
BMSK0011520.1	-3.4673	0.0004
BMSK0010494.1	-3.8580	0.0005
BMSK0008123.1	-1.9251	0.0005
BMSK0009133.1	-1.5790	0.0005
BMSK0003728.1	-2.6290	0.0005
BMSK0013571.1	-2.4587	0.0005
BMSK0003465.1	-1.4316	0.0005
BMSK0003259.1	-1.6442	0.0005
BMSK0010659.1	-4.2472	0.0005
BMSK0006759.1	-4.0378	0.0005
BMSK0003099.1	-2.6224	0.0006
BMSK0001677.1	-2.3410	0.0006
BMSK0011576.1	-1.0992	0.0006
BMSK0003513.1	-2.7917	0.0006
BMSK0015417.1	-3.1946	0.0006
BMSK0002900.1	-2.9235	0.0007
BMSK0015284.1	-3.2917	0.0007
BMSK0011037.1	-1.8433	0.0007
BMSK0004221.1	-5.7870	0.0007
BMSK0014605.1	-5.2513	0.0007
BMSK0012164.1	-1.8102	0.0008
BMSK0002868.1	-1.3759	0.0008
BMSK0006430.1	-2.3019	0.0008
BMSK0010047.1	-1.3523	0.0008
BMSK0010119.1	-5.7164	0.0008
BMSK0013323.1	-5.6085	0.0008
BMSK0013132.1	-1.8183	0.0008
BMSK0010431.1	-4.1958	0.0008
BMSK0012980.1	-1.6647	0.0008
BMSK0011842.1	-2.1639	0.0008
BMSK0001903.1	-2.4772	0.0008
BMSK0012809.1	-1.8334	0.0009
BMSK0015080.1	-1.4945	0.0009
BMSK0004089.1	-2.1721	0.0009
BMSK0008922.1	-1.2052	0.0009
BMSK0015665.1	-2.8898	0.0010
BMSK0012816.1	-2.4794	0.0010
BMSK0002783.1	-1.7140	0.0010
BMSK0011412.1	-1.7939	0.0010
BMSK0005177.1	-3.5905	0.0010
BMSK0010951.1	-3.2691	0.0010
BMSK0006477.1	-1.1241	0.0010
BMSK0002785.1	-1.1705	0.0010
BMSK0012554.1	-1.7418	0.0010
BMSK0004477.1	-2.9060	0.0010
BMSK0006885.1	-2.2583	0.0011
BMSK0009224.1	-5.8378	0.0011

BMSK0006895.1	-4.8479	0.0011
BMSK0014104.1	-5.3855	0.0011
BMSK0009375.1	-1.7759	0.0011
BMSK0001762.1	-1.0275	0.0011
BMSK0015632.1	-4.0089	0.0011
BMSK0003816.1	-2.5487	0.0011
BMSK0013616.1	-3.6658	0.0011
BMSK0003658.1	-4.5513	0.0012
BMSK0000902.1	-1.8570	0.0012
BMSK0003336.1	-5.5623	0.0012
BMSK0006628.1	-2.0067	0.0012
BMSK0016018.1	-3.3290	0.0012
BMSK0012985.1	-1.4498	0.0012
BMSK0007186.1	-3.8877	0.0012
BMSK0013141.1	-3.4995	0.0012
BMSK0015239.1	-6.0799	0.0013
BMSK0008080.1	-3.0028	0.0013
BMSK0004703.1	-2.3982	0.0013
BMSK0009651.1	-1.6375	0.0013
BMSK0003071.1	-3.5778	0.0014
BMSK0001681.1	-1.9667	0.0015
BMSK0014124.1	-2.4720	0.0015
BMSK0002223.1	-1.4390	0.0015
BMSK0005169.1	-2.4157	0.0015
BMSK0005147.1	-1.7011	0.0015
BMSK0013281.1	-3.2146	0.0016
BMSK0001370.1	-4.2489	0.0016
BMSK0010536.1	-1.4046	0.0016
BMSK0003457.1	-3.3474	0.0016
BMSK0000594.1	-1.4382	0.0016
BMSK0008083.1	-3.8989	0.0016
BMSK0011132.1	-3.8353	0.0017
BMSK0001680.1	-2.5452	0.0017
BMSK0005473.1	-1.7297	0.0017
BMSK0009444.1	-2.6343	0.0017
BMSK0014787.1	-2.0267	0.0017
BMSK0012579.1	-3.0873	0.0017
BMSK0009629.1	-5.0885	0.0018
BMSK0013033.1	-2.2037	0.0018
BMSK0015675.1	-1.9168	0.0018
BMSK0015783.1	-1.2129	0.0019
BMSK0005297.1	-1.1957	0.0019
BMSK0013199.1	-2.2001	0.0019
BMSK0010525.1	-2.5729	0.0019
BMSK0005582.1	-2.3147	0.0019
BMSK0006485.1	-3.7012	0.0020
BMSK0009990.1	-1.1658	0.0020
BMSK0013018.1	-2.1127	0.0020
BMSK0010549.1	-1.5025	0.0020
BMSK0000750.1	-1.3431	0.0021
BMSK0013971.1	-2.5611	0.0021
BMSK0005702.1	-1.9834	0.0021
BMSK0010013.1	-4.8393	0.0021
BMSK0006068.1	-2.5917	0.0021
BMSK0007905.1	-1.0324	0.0021
BMSK0011680.1	-1.3596	0.0022
BMSK0007402.1	-5.5632	0.0022
BMSK0001678.1	-2.2013	0.0022
BMSK0011571.1	-2.9838	0.0023
BMSK0014056.1	-1.4279	0.0023
BMSK0006131.1	-1.7770	0.0023
BMSK0009417.1	-5.6937	0.0023
BMSK0009586.1	-1.4721	0.0024

BMSK0008909.1	-1.7680	0.0025
BMSK0010253.1	-1.3309	0.0025
BMSK0002359.1	-1.3168	0.0025
BMSK0004115.1	-1.1408	0.0025
BMSK0015701.1	-1.7481	0.0025
BMSK0009901.1	-1.5256	0.0025
BMSK0009167.1	-2.1711	0.0027
BMSK0001228.1	-3.3240	0.0027
BMSK0006287.1	-2.6653	0.0027
BMSK0015580.1	-4.7849	0.0028
BMSK0011947.1	-2.4691	0.0028
BMSK0007234.1	-1.8961	0.0028
BMSK0013727.1	-1.4311	0.0029
BMSK0007283.1	-1.9750	0.0029
BMSK0008363.1	-1.1420	0.0030
BMSK0008988.1	-1.0319	0.0030
BMSK0011525.1	-5.3521	0.0031
BMSK0009024.1	-2.2166	0.0032
BMSK0000257.1	-1.7315	0.0032
BMSK0015278.1	-3.6916	0.0032
BMSK0011760.1	-5.3197	0.0032
BMSK0013130.1	-1.4348	0.0033
BMSK0009624.1	-3.3179	0.0033
BMSK0004694.1	-1.8444	0.0033
BMSK0008443.1	-1.1894	0.0033
BMSK0015366.1	-1.1023	0.0034
BMSK0004546.1	-2.2166	0.0035
BMSK0012178.1	-1.4548	0.0036
BMSK0009248.1	-2.6590	0.0036
BMSK0008141.1	-2.1156	0.0036
BMSK0004754.1	-2.7580	0.0036
BMSK0005762.1	-2.2673	0.0037
BMSK0013016.1	-2.0507	0.0038
BMSK0015727.1	-1.3939	0.0039
BMSK0010819.1	-5.2536	0.0039
BMSK0006504.1	-2.1699	0.0040
BMSK0004343.1	-4.1140	0.0040
BMSK0004628.1	-1.5649	0.0041
BMSK0015720.1	-2.7052	0.0043
BMSK0001913.1	-4.4041	0.0043
BMSK0009907.1	-1.8432	0.0043
BMSK0007066.1	-1.8786	0.0044
BMSK0004755.1	-1.9500	0.0044
BMSK0012040.1	-1.0391	0.0045
BMSK0009349.1	-3.1649	0.0045
BMSK0013031.1	-2.5922	0.0046
BMSK0011949.1	-1.4979	0.0047
BMSK0009732.1	-2.4581	0.0048
BMSK0009964.1	-2.6878	0.0048
BMSK0012981.1	-1.2825	0.0048
BMSK0011410.1	-3.1094	0.0049
BMSK0014371.1	-2.1487	0.0049
BMSK0015777.1	-1.8418	0.0050
BMSK0001988.1	-1.9441	0.0050
BMSK0013346.1	-1.8296	0.0051
BMSK0009079.1	-1.0647	0.0051
BMSK0002215.1	-4.5767	0.0051
BMSK0011350.1	-1.2801	0.0051
BMSK0003096.1	-2.2570	0.0052
BMSK0012982.1	-1.9461	0.0052
BMSK0005606.1	-3.9863	0.0053
BMSK0011841.1	-2.2995	0.0053
BMSK0001272.1	-1.9406	0.0053

BMSK0004273.1	-1.0864	0.0054
BMSK0005729.1	-1.1928	0.0055
BMSK0010316.1	-1.0958	0.0055
BMSK0002882.1	-1.0370	0.0055
BMSK0010857.1	-1.2024	0.0056
BMSK0000365.1	-1.5814	0.0056
BMSK0014491.1	-2.4829	0.0056
BMSK0008194.1	-2.6535	0.0057
BMSK0009023.1	-2.0956	0.0059
BMSK0013435.1	-1.2544	0.0059
BMSK0004698.1	-2.5184	0.0059
BMSK0003488.1	-2.2588	0.0059
BMSK0013017.1	-2.2026	0.0060
BMSK0013301.1	-1.0765	0.0060
BMSK0006046.1	-1.9329	0.0060
BMSK0013875.1	-2.7623	0.0061
BMSK0009508.1	-1.6447	0.0061
BMSK0001193.1	-1.4571	0.0061
BMSK0014139.1	-2.2466	0.0062
BMSK0010299.1	-2.5128	0.0062
BMSK0006134.1	-2.8336	0.0063
BMSK0011840.1	-2.3390	0.0063
BMSK0004276.1	-1.9779	0.0064
BMSK0007972.1	-1.9012	0.0064
BMSK0011746.1	-2.9306	0.0065
BMSK0005144.1	-1.4810	0.0066
BMSK0010313.1	-2.3998	0.0066
BMSK0007284.1	-1.6976	0.0066
BMSK0006883.1	-1.8633	0.0066
BMSK0006010.1	-1.1644	0.0067
BMSK0006593.1	-1.0494	0.0067
BMSK0011242.1	-1.0939	0.0071
BMSK0000981.1	-1.8587	0.0071
BMSK0005113.1	-1.1435	0.0072
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